

COMPETENCY REQUIREMENTS OF INDUSTRY FOR PRE-SERVICE STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS BASED ON TESDA-TRAINING REGULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the competency requirements of the industry for pre-service students in technical-vocational schools, guided by TESDA Training Regulations. The study explored the profile of selected industry partners, focusing on business type and length of operation. It assessed the perceived importance of pre-service competencies by bread and pastry business owners and restaurant owners and compared the importance of these competencies based on the businesses' profiles. The subjects were 50 bread and pastry business owners and 50 cookery industry partners associated with technical and vocational schools in the school division offices of City of Ilagan and Isabela. A modified and adopted questionnaire was utilized for data collection. The findings revealed that micro-type bread and pastry businesses had been operating for less than two years, while macro-type cookery businesses had been running for over two years. Bread and pastry business owners emphasized the importance of trainees' skills in preparing, decorating, presenting, and storing bakery and pastry products during on-the-job training. On the other hand, restaurant owners prioritized the competency of cleanliness and maintenance in various premises where diverse dishes and appetizers are prepared, with a particular focus on side dishes rather than main dishes. The study found no significant difference in the perceived importance of pre-service competencies based on the type of business. Additionally, no significant difference was found between the learned competencies of on-the-job trainees and the length of business operation as perceived by restaurant owners, except for the emphasis on cleanliness and kitchen maintenance by restaurant business owners.

Keywords: *Competency, Industry Partners, Industry Owners/Managers, Macro-Business, Micro-Business, Pre-service Students, Senior High School, Technical Vocational Track, Technical and Vocational Schools*

INTRODUCTION

One of the aspirations of every Filipino family for their children is to have a better education for them to have stable job in the future. Many parents believe that good education will improve one's economic status. In a poverty-stricken nation like the Philippines the importance of education is emphasized by society. In all nations over the world, education is given a high value probably because it is perceived by the masses that it gives hopes most especially to the grass roots level of the society and serves as a stepping stone out of poverty, it is imagined by the middle classes as a way to climb to a higher social status, and is used by the ruling classes to reinforce their influence over the populace. Likewise, education occupies a central place in Philippine political, economic, social and cultural life. It has always been strongly viewed as a pillar of national development and a primary avenue for social and economic mobility.

The abovementioned statement shows that education and job are interrelated since education affects job or the other depends on the other. In a narrow sense, getting an education is one's ticket to have a better and successful life in the future. From this viewpoint, education and training of students are so important in the development of their knowledge, attitudes, skills, and habits. In the end, they will acquire the job competencies that meet industry standards and to be job-ready in today's new economic order.

Ten thousand of college graduates join the country's workforce year after year. Statistically, the unemployment rate in the Philippines is projected to be 6.2 percent by the end of the year 2019. From 1994 to 2015 the average of unemployment rate has been 8.78 percent, way higher than the neighboring countries in the Asia Pacific Region. In Malaysia, the average unemployment rate is 3.4 percent; in Thailand, 2.3 percent; in Singapore, 3.4 percent; in Vietnam, 5.6 percent; China, 3.9 percent; and in Taiwan, 4.3 percent. Only in Indonesia has an unemployment rate close to the Philippines that is 8.9 percent.

The Philippine Institute for Development Studies said that in the Philippines, unemployment is a time bomb. Between 2005 and 2030, the labor force will increase from 32 million to about 52 million. It is puzzling in some sectors, there are many available jobs, but few to fill up the vacancies. In the food sector, for instance, there is a shortage of workers with skills in cooking, food preservation, etc. Generally, companies' difficulty searching for accountants, bookkeepers, competent drivers, among others. Studies revealed that 22 percent of the unemployed have attended college while 19 percent have graduated from college. This figure indicates a serious disconnection between what schools teach and the demand of the jobs market. Students are not acquiring the skills

they need to fill up available jobs when they graduate. Schools still offer, and students still enroll in, traditional courses without so much as examining the demand of industries.

However, more than the disconnection between education and the need of industries, the real cause of massive unemployment in the Philippines can be blamed on the quality of education and the quality of graduates that the government is producing. The literacy rate in the Philippines during the olden days is always on top, but, as years passed, the Philippine literacy rate keeps on decreasing. From the recent report of the Programmed for International Student Assessment (PISA) Philippines scored the lowest in reading comprehension in the 2018. Reading proficiency is essential for a wide variety of human activities - from following instructions in a manual; to finding out the who, what, when, where, and why of an event; to communicating with others for a specific purpose or transaction.

Despite the fact that the country's educational status keeps on decreasing when compared to other nations, the government makes its best to compete and keep up with the international standard in order to gain the prestige when it comes to education. One educational program that the government has implemented is the K to 12 program which aims to enhance learners' basic skills, produce more competent citizens, and prepare graduates for lifelong learning and employment.

The K to 12 program offers a decongested 12-year program that gives students sufficient time to master skills and absorb basic competencies. Students of this program will graduate at legal age and ready for employment, entrepreneurship, middle level skills development, and higher education upon graduation. The new curriculum gives students the chance to choose among three tracks: academic, sports and arts; and technical vocational and undergo immersion which provides relevant exposure and actual experience in their chosen track. Also, graduates of this program will be accelerated and recognized in other countries.

The technical vocational and livelihood track is one of the highlights of the new curriculum where technical and vocational schools prepare students in the world of employment. In realizing this objective, necessary competencies are taught and given ample time to apply it in their work immersion or in their on-the-job training to assess their skills if they are ready to face the marketplace after finishing senior high school.

In line with this marketplace demand, education and training of would-be workers is crucial. To keep pace with the fast-changing needs of industries, in-school preparation of students requires various learning experiences that will hone students' academic capabilities. Equally important is the hands-on training of students to expose them to real work situation. Thus, teaching them the skills, knowledge and competencies that are needed for employees to perform a specific job within the workplace and work environment. Acob (2011) explained that industry exposure equips students with the necessary skills so that they would be job-ready when they graduate. Acob further emphasized that to be able to fulfill this significant task, it is the responsibility of the

educational institutions to equip students with the necessary skills thru relevant in-campus training at par with the requirements of industry.

Orbeta Jr, Lagarto, Ortiz and Potestad (2018) assessed the likelihood of achieving the employment and entrepreneurship objectives of the program by examining the experience of the Grade 12 graduating students and the views of firms about the labor market prospects of the senior high school graduates. It does this by looking into the SHS curriculum and the competencies developed, identifying the types of jobs that fit the Grade 12 graduates, gathering the perspective on the jobs available and appropriate for the grade 12 graduates and providing policy recommendations for the improvement of the implementation of the SHS program. The result of the study revealed that despite identifying employment and entrepreneurship as a rationale for the program, three quarters of the Grade 12 students plan to proceed to higher education. This proportion is true even for those in the TVL track. Among the highlights of the FGD with the students is the revelation that they are not very confident that they will get a job after graduating from SHS.

In a research study conducted by Abas and Imam (2016) on graduates' competence on employability skills and job performance, they presented that the study has unearthed that not all categories of employability skills are relevant to the employees advance their contextual performance and become successful in work place. However, employees who have competencies in specific employability skills that are aligned with their contextual behaviors will put them in an advantageous position to stay and progress in progress in work places and become attuned to the challenging demands of different work situations.

According to Demitillo (2016) the TVL implementation in the K to12 curriculum revealed that TLE program implementation were to a great extent implemented by school heads and teachers. Further, there was no significant difference in the extent of implementation whether the respondents are school head or teacher.

According to Wu, Bai and Zhu (2019) there are three training modalities being implemented in partnership with companies/establishments. These are Apprenticeship Program, Learnership Program, and Dual Training System (DTS). Enterprise-based TVET aims to combine the training at workplaces and theoretical teaching at schools. Course systems are established according to enterprises' talent demands to train qualified talents meeting enterprise demands.

With the K to 12 career program, educators and parents are optimistic that the country's future high school graduates will be able to maximize their talents and potentials, and take their careers into the next level.

Being world-class high-school graduates means having a tremendous opportunity to boost the students' creativity, considering how they can innovate with today's advanced technology. With the proper guidance and support, the next batches of college graduates in the country can very well compete with graduates from any university in the world.

In the end, TVL track plays a very important role in preparing students towards their future career. This track is their ticket to have a better and stable working life. With these bases, the researcher was convinced and motivated to conduct this study to determine the different competencies gained during the in-school training of students specifically in the field of Food Service Management. These pre-service competencies are the competencies they will carry during their on-the-job training in the industry.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to determine the competency requirements of industry for pre-service students of Technical Vocational Schools on TESDA-Training Regulations in the school's division offices of City of Ilagan and Isabela as perceived by the industry owners.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the selected industry partners in terms of:
 - a. type of business; and
 - b. length of operation?
2. What is the level of importance of the pre-service competencies of Pre-service students as perceived by:
 - a. bread and pastry owners; and
 - b. restaurant owners?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by the bread and pastry owners and restaurant owners when grouped according to profile?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design and methodology employed to determine the competency and required industry job competency of on-the-job training students in the technical-vocational schools. It consists of the research method and design, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment of data.

Research Method and Design

The quantitative method using a descriptive research design was used in this study to determine the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the pre-service students as perceived by the industry owner-respondents.

Qualitative survey method through an interview was likewise employed to get a deeper understanding on the highly required remarks on various competency level in bread and pastry production and in commercial cooking.

Respondents of the Study

This study was conducted in selected industry partners of technical vocational schools in the province of Isabela. The schools involved in this study were the three (3) technical vocational schools in the schools division of City of Ilagan, Isabela namely: Isabela School of Arts and Trade; San Rafael National and Vocational High School; San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School; and two (2) schools were from the schools division of Isabela namely: Reina Mercedes Vocational and Industrial School in Reina Mercedes, Isabela; and San Mateo Vocational and Industrial School in San Mateo, Isabela.

The respondents were the owners or managers of the industry partners in the field of food and management as shown in the list below.

No.	Bread and Pastry Production	Cookery
1.	Dulce De San Jose	Mangi Foodhouz
2.	Zhels Breads and Butter	Tabin's Cuisine
3.	Rona's Bakery	Mike's Lechon and Restaurant
4.	Hi Five	Soccoro Restaurant
5.	Denna's Bakery	Otep's Tinuno
6.	Abrenica's	The Simple Table
7.	AJ Bakery	Ancheta's Food Park
8.	Marvin Joy	Excel
9.	Padilla's Bakery	Melting Pot
10.	Cindys Bakery	La Perfecta
11.	Mei Mei Bakeshop	Hardin Grills and Restaurants
12.	JVM Bread Hauz	Felicity's
13.	Laida's Bakery	Bert's Place
14.	Regunda Bakery	Classic Burger
15.	Sanitary Bakeshop	Winnie's Grill
16.	Lordbe's Bakery	Bites and Slices Foodhub
17.	New Cleto's Mart and Bakeshop	Superior Restaurant
18.	J's Hot Buko Roll Bakery and Delicacies	Tita Ludy's Garden Café
19.	Red Ribbon Bakeshop	King Angelo Restaurant

20.	Girlie's Bakeshop and Bread House	Chef Albert and Marco Restaurant
21.	Cristobal's Bakery	Garden Vista Event's Place
22.	The Maigne Baker	Bahay Kubo Kitchenette
23.	Mr. Bakers Bakeshop	K8c10 Restaurant
24.	Family Bakery	Crispee On The Fly Ilagan
25.	Bread House	Bukid Kainan at Ihaw-Ihaw
26.	The Leidi Chef	Piazza Zecarelli Hoetl and Restaurants
27.	R. M Mamauag Bakery	Joys Place and Restaurants
28.	Mang Kevin's Bakeshop	Clancy's Restaurants
29.	Marylois Bakery	Kabayan's Grill
30.	Calamagui Bakery	Kusina Kawayan
31.	Mrs. G Bakeshop	JC Restaurant and Grill
32.	MC&co. Delight	Marco Paulo Café & Restaurant
33.	La Residencia Espineli	Rykas Restaurant
34.	Sadiri Special Hopia	D'spot Railpark
35.	Clake's Bakeshop	The Lady Purple Restaurant
36.	Marian's Bakery	Queen Jennifer Hotel & Restaurant
37.	Hi QQ Bakery	Bristo de Grande
38.	Regunda Bakery	Charizas Rstaurant
39.	Julie's Bakeshop	Hazel's Place Restaurant
40.	Jemong's Pandesal	The Blanket
41.	Rivera's Bakery	Remy's Garden & Restaurant
42.	Kristine Bakeshop	Salido Restaurant
43.	Cherrie's Bakeshop	Umaykan Grill & Restaurants
44.	Aunt Joie's Patisserie	Jack's Kitchenette
45.	ANDRHIYA's Cakes and Pastries	Dine N' Zolo Restaurant
46.	Tienda Y Panaderia Santiago	Kuya J Restaurant
47.	Rockwell's Café and Bakery	Bayani Café and Restaurant

48.	Marquez Bakery	Marilen Food Plaza
49.	Pandezab	Santiago Restaurant
50.	Wall's Native Cakes	Jomar's Place

Research Instrument

The most important components of a research study are the research instruments because it gathers or collect data for information. The researcher modified and adapted the competency guide used by the schools under the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority and Technical and Vocational Schools of the Department of Education.

The competency guide was modified and adapted and used as the questionnaire of this study. Two modified and adapted questionnaires were prepared, one for the bread and pastry business-owners and the other one is for the cookery business-owners.

The questionnaire for the bread and pastry owners was categorized into two parts. Part I focused on the profile of the business owner-respondents while Part II focused on the competency level in bread and pastry production which includes the following: preparing and producing bakery products; preparing and producing pastry products; preparing and presenting gateaux, tortes and cakes; preparing and displaying petits fours; and presenting desserts.

The questionnaire for the cookery owners was also categorized into two parts: Part I focused on the profile of the business owner-respondents while Part II focused on the competency level in cookery which includes the following: cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises; preparing stocks, sauces and soups; preparing appetizers; preparing salads and dressings; preparing sandwiches; preparing meat dishes; preparing vegetable dishes; prepare egg dishes; preparing starch dishes; preparing poultry and game dishes; preparing seafood dishes; preparing desserts; and packaging prepared food.

Data Gathering Procedure

All information gathered was kept confidential. All data collected were carefully studied for reliability and consistency to avail at the essential relevant to this study.

The researcher undertook the following steps and procedures in gathering the most important data: Firstly, the researcher identified existing problems that needed immediate and sustainable solutions, from the problems identified, the researcher formulated the title of this study; Secondly, the researcher identified the selected industry partners of the technical vocational schools and the managers or owners served as the respondents of this study; Thirdly, the researcher adapted and modified the research instrument and prepared a request letter to conduct the study and send it to the Schools Division Superintendents of Ilagan City and Isabela; Next, copies of endorsement letter

from the two Offices of the Schools Division Superintendents were personally given to the school heads or school administrators in the selected public secondary technical-vocational schools in the province of Isabela and an initial interview to the principals and teachers were conducted; Fifthly, the researcher prepared another letter and personally handed together with the questionnaire to the managers or owners of the selected industry partners and directly oriented the business owner-respondents on how to accomplish the said questionnaire, after answering the questionnaire an interview was conducted to the selected industry-managers/owners regarding the required competencies needed by the pre-service students in their on-the-job training; Next, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires and brought to the statistician for the data treatment using the different research statistical tools; and Finally, the data gathered were analyzed, interpreted, summarized, concluded and recommendations were formulated.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

In order to analyze the obtained data, the following statistical tools were used by the researcher.

1. Frequency counts and percentages were used in describing the profile of the selected industry partners.
2. Weighted Average Mean was used to analyze the level of importance of the different learning outcomes included in each of the pre-service competencies of the on-the-job training students.
3. To determine the importance of the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by the industry owners a Likert scale with corresponding quantitative range and adjectival description was used as follows:

Scale	Range	Adjectival Description
5	4.24 – 5.00	Highly Required
4	3.43 – 4.23	Required
3	2.62 – 3.42	Moderately Required
2	1.81 – 2.61	Slightly Required
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not Required

4. One Way Between Groups Analysis of Variance (*ANOVA*) was used to determine the relationship in the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students and the significant difference between the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students in terms of the type of business and length of operation of the industry partners.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on determining the Competency Requirements of Industry for Pre-Service Students of Technical Vocational Schools on TESDA-Training Regulation in the school's division offices of City of Ilagan and Isabela as perceived by the industry

owners for school year 2019-2020. Selected technical-vocational schools and industry partners were involved in the study.

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered following the sequence of the statement of the problem as well as the objectives and the hypothesis of the study.

Table 1. Profile of the selected industry partners in terms of types of business and length of operation

	Profile	Bread and Pastry		Cookery	
		F	%	f	%
Types of Business	Micro	37	74.0	16	32.0
	Macro	13	26.0	34	68.0
	Total	50	100.0	50	100.0
Length of Operation	two years and below of operation	30	60.0	22	44.0
	more than 2 years of operation	20	40.0	28	56.0
	Total	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 1 presents the profile of the selected industry partners in terms of types of business and length of operation. It revealed in the table that out of 50 respondents there were 37 or 74 percent respondents of the bread and pastry industries fall under the micro type of business while majority of the cookery industries fall under the macro type of business which has 34 or 68 percent respondents. This implies that most of the bread and pastry business owners engage in a microbusiness type which means that the business they are operating is classified small business while most of the cookery business owners engage in a macro business type which means they are operating a bigger type of business.

As to the length of operating the business, the table shows that majority of the bread and pastry businesses are operating less than two years and most of the cookery businesses are operating more than two years. This further shows that only few bread and pastry businesses are established while most of the cookery businesses are already established industries.

Table 2. Level of importance of the pre-service competency of the pre-service Students as perceived by bread and pastry owners

Unit of Competency	Learning Outcomes	Mean	Remark
1. Prepare and produce bakery products.	a. Prepare bakery products b. Decorate and present bakery products c. Store bakery products	4.64	Highly required
2. Prepare and produce pastry products	a. Prepare pastry products b. Decorate and present pastry products b. Store pastry products	4.60	Highly required
3. Prepare and present gateaux, tortes and cakes	a. Prepare sponge and cakes b. Prepare and use fillings c. Decorate cakes d. Present cakes e. Store cakes	4.22	Required
4. Prepare and display petits fours	a. Prepare iced petits fours b. Prepare fresh petits fours c. Prepare marzipan petits fours d. Prepare caramelized petits fours e. Display petits fours f. Store petits fours	4.08	Required
5. Present desserts	a. Prepare and serve plated desserts b. Plan, prepare and present dessert buffet selection or plating c. Store and package desserts	4.14	Required
General Weighted Mean		4.34	Highly Required

Table 2 shows the level of importance of the Pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by bread and pastry owners.

The table disclosed that preparing and producing bakery and pastry products are highly required competencies for bread and pastry owners as reflected in their respective means of 4.64 and 4.60. This implies that pre-service students are highly expected to prepare, decorate and present, and store bakery and pastry products while they are undergoing on-the-job training. Meanwhile, preparing and presenting gateaux, tortes and cakes, preparing and displaying petits fours, and presenting desserts are required by the bread and pastry owners as reflected in their respective means. This implies that it is a requirement for the Pre-service students to prepare sponge and cakes; prepare and use fillings; decorate, present, and store cakes; prepare iced and fresh petits fours; prepare marzipan and caramelized petits fours; display and store petits fours; prepare and serve

plated desserts; plan, prepare, and present dessert buffet selection or plating; and store and package desserts.

With this, bread and pastry owners are more into preparing and producing bakery and pastry products than preparing and producing cakes and desserts products. However, the data generally reveals that preparing and producing variant types of products from cake and pastry industries are in their utmost level of importance since the general weighted mean is 4.34 and interpreted as highly required.

This finding supports the statement of respondents 1,3,5,8 and 9 during the interview part here stated that “in bread and pastry owner clearly stated that in his industry it requires only on preparing and producing bakery products, preparing and producing pastry products because these are very essential competencies needed in his own industry. Likewise, the owner rated the other competencies required because someday the industry will need an employee who has a basic knowledge of these competencies.”

This finding further agrees to the finding of the study conducted by Cristobal (2008) where he found out that on-the-job training is a good program for augmenting the knowledge, skills and competencies of the task and activities for included in the on-the-job training are routine that do not really require the application of the higher knowledge, skills and competencies learned in the classroom. With these findings, the very essence of attending the on-the-job training is to apply and implement the necessary competencies acquired in order to help the industry partners become successful.

Table 3. Level of importance of the pre-service competency of the pre-service students as perceived by restaurant owners

Unit of Competency	Learning Outcomes	Mean	Remark
1. Clean and maintain kitchen premises	a. Clean, sanitize and store equipment	4.75	Highly required
	b. Clean and sanitize premises		
	c. Dispose of waste		
2. Prepare stocks, sauces and soups	a. Prepare stocks, glazes and essences required for menu items	4.64	Highly required
	b. Prepare soups required for menu items		
	c. Prepare sauces required for menu items		
	d. Store and reconstitute stocks, sauces and soups		
3. Prepare appetizers	a. Perform Mise' en place	4.50	Highly required
	b. Prepare a range of appetizers		
	c. Present a range of appetizers		
	d. Store appetizers		

4. Prepare salads and dressings	a. Perform Mise en place b. Prepare a variety salads and dressings c. Present a variety of salads and dressings d. Store salads and dressings	4.40	Highly required
5. Prepare sandwiches	a. Perform Mise en place b. Prepare a variety of sandwiches c. Present a variety of sandwiches d. Store sandwiches	4.30	Highly required
6. Prepare meat dishes	a. Perform Mise en place b. Cook meat cuts for service c. Present meat cuts for service d. Store meat	4.64	Highly required
7. Prepare vegetables dishes	a. Perform Mise en place b. Prepare vegetable dishes c. Present vegetable dishes d. Store vegetables dishes	4.62	Highly required
8. Prepare egg dishes	a. Perform Mise en place b. Prepare and cook egg dishes c. Present egg dishes d. Store egg dishes	4.06	Required
9. Prepare starch dishes	a. Perform Mise en place b. Prepare starch dishes c. Present Starch dishes d. Store Starch dishes	3.94	Required
10. Prepare poultry and game dishes	a. Perform mise en place b. Cook poultry and game dishes c. Plate/present poultry and game dishes d. Store poultry and game	4.06	Required
11. Prepare seafood dishes	a. Perform mise en place b. Handle fish and seafood c. Cook fish and shellfish d. Plate/Present fish and seafood e. Store fish and seafood	4.02	Required
12. Prepare desserts	a. Perform mise en place b. Prepare desserts and sweet sauces c. Plate/Present desserts d. Store desserts	4.64	Highly required
General Weighted Mean		4.38	Highly Required

Table 3 shows the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by restaurant owners.

From the table, it is shown that the following competencies were highly required with their corresponding means: cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises (4.75); preparing stocks, sauces and soups (4.64); preparing meat dishes (4.64); preparing desserts (4.64); preparing appetizers (4.50); preparing salads and dressings (4.40); preparing sandwiches (4.30); and preparing vegetable dishes (4.62). The remaining competencies with their corresponding mean are required as perceived by the restaurant owners: preparing egg dishes (4.06); preparing poultry and game dishes (4.06); preparing seafood dishes (4.02); and preparing starch dishes (3.94).

Thus, restaurant owners were most concerned with the competency on cleanliness and its maintenances in the various premises of the restaurants where workers prepare variant types of dishes, appetizers and many more. Restaurant owners also perceived the higher importance of preparing sides dishes than preparing the main dishes in the restaurants. However, the data generally reveals that all of the competencies are in their utmost level of importance since the general weighted mean is 4.38 and interpreted as highly required.

This finding supports the statement of respondents 1,2,4,6 and 7 under restaurant owners during the interview, “the competencies with highly required remarks are the basic competencies under core competencies in cookery industry to be learned or acquired by the pre-service students in their respective schools and most especially these are the competencies needed in this kind of industry.”

Likewise, this finding agrees to what Wahha (2016) discussed in his article. In any job / occupation can be effectively and sufficiently described in terms of the tasks that successful workers in that occupation perform; all tasks have direct implications for the awareness, knowledge, skills, and attitudes; competencies that workers / trainees must acquire in order to perform the tasks correctly; assessment is made on how the individual is actually performing work; an individual is incompetent no matter how much knowledge he has, as long as he can't apply his knowledge and skills appropriately at work location; the assessment must be objective by conducting it against defined Competency Standards.

Table 4. Comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the pre-service students as perceived by bread and pastry owners when grouped according to type of business

Competency	f-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Interpretation
1. Prepare and produce bakery products	3.326	0.074	$0.074 > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not significant
2. Prepare and produce pastry products	0.017	0.898	$0.898 > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not significant

3.	Prepare and present gateaux, tortes and cakes	1.419	0.239	0.239 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
4.	Prepare and display petits fours	0.347	0.559	0.559 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
5.	Present desserts	0.008	0.929	0.929 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant

Table 4 shows the comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by bread and pastry owners when grouped according to type of business

As presented in the table, the p-values of all the competencies are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, accept the null hypothesis since it was interpreted as not significant. It is therefore concluded that regardless as to the type of business it has no significant difference on the level of importance of the Pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by bread and pastry owners.

This finding supports what Langga (2015) found in her study where the mismatch between the competencies that BTTE-FSM students acquired in school and those that they applied during immersion was not caused by a mismatch between the curriculum and industry requirements. Rather it was caused by other factors. First, some of the selected industries for immersion were fast food stores that required the trainees to do only simple tasks as getting orders and entertaining guests. Second, industry partners were not well-oriented on the competencies that students needed to apply during immersion. This gap caused supervisors to assign tasks that were not really in line with the competency needs of trainees. Perhaps a regular visit from the school while students were still on immersion, could have speedily addressed these gaps. But the lack of monitoring from the school was also one of the gaps identified.

Table 5. Comparison in the Level of Importance of the Pre-Service Competency of the Pre-service Students as Perceived by Bread and Pastry Owners when Grouped according to Length of Operation

Competency	f-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Interpretation
1. Prepare and produce bakery products	0.014	0.907	0.907 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
2. Prepare and produce pastry products	0.336	0.565	0.565 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant

3. Prepare and present gateaux, tortes and cakes	0.626	0.433	0.433 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
4. Prepare and display petits fours	0.505	0.481	0.481 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
5. Present desserts	0.128	0.972	0.972 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant

Table 5 presents the comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competencies from the learning outcomes of the on-the-job training students as perceived by bread and pastry owners when grouped according to length of operation. It revealed in the table that the p values of all the competencies are greater than the alpha which is 0.05 and are all interpreted not significant therefore, accept the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Regardless as to the length of operation, there is no significant difference in the level of importance of the Pre-service competency of the Pre-service students as perceived by the bread and pastry owners.

This finding is somewhat similar to the findings of Bodo (2018) when he evaluated the Status of the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Technology Program of Eastern Visayas State University and he found out that the BSHRT student respondents are young; majority are female; and majority are holders of NC II in Food and Beverage and Cookery. The acquisition of Competencies in HRT in Basic, Common and Core competencies were rated “to a great extent”; The laboratory tools and equipment of the Hotel and Restaurant Technology Program are “available but not functional”; Student-respondents rated “very strong” for the Local and International linkages of the BSHRT Program. Among the paired variables, bar equipment and NC II Certificate are significantly correlated. Food and Beverage Services–Dinner wares, cloth and other linens and gender are also significantly correlated. Front Office Services paired with gender is significantly correlated, laboratory tools and equipment, dinnerware are significantly correlated with common competencies. Bartending, dinner wares, cutleries and front office service equipment are significantly correlated with core competencies and gender is significantly correlated with the status of the local and international linkages. As to the implementation of the BSHRT Program, student respondents cited “Obsolete teaching strategies” as the number one problem encountered in curriculum and instruction. In faculty, “lack of supervision during laboratory activities” ranked first. In laboratory tools and equipment, “lack of laboratory tools and equipment” was identified as the main problem encountered, in library, “the lack of references, recipe books, journals and magazines” were the only problems cited. On linkages, “lack of industry linkages for OJT” was the only problem met and lastly, “lack of implementing policies in OJT” was also the only problem identified.

Table 6. Comparison in the Level of Importance of the Pre-Service Competency of the Pre-service Students as Perceived by Restaurant Owners when Grouped according to Type of Business

Competency	f-value	p-value	Comparison n	Decision	Interpretation
1. Clean and maintain kitchen premises	5.064	0.029	0.029 < 0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
2. Prepare stocks, sauces and soups	2.002	0.164	0.164 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
3. Prepare appetizers	1.455	0.234	0.234 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
4. Prepare salads and dressings	1.455	0.234	0.234 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
5. Prepare sandwiches	1.006	0.321	0.321 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
6. Prepare meat dishes	2.002	0.164	0.164 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
7. Prepare vegetables dishes	1.421	0.239	0.239 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
8. Prepare egg dishes	3.860	0.055	0.055 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
9. Prepare starch dishes	1.272	0.265	0.265 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
10. Prepare poultry and game dishes	1.476	0.230	0.230 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
11. Prepare seafood dishes	1.639	0.207	0.207 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
12. Prepare desserts	3.689	0.061	0.061 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
13. Package prepared food	1.486	0.229	0.229 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant

1.1. Table 6 shows the comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competencies from the learning outcomes of the on-the-job training students as perceived by restaurant owners when grouped according to type of business

The table revealed from the results that the significance of p-values of all the competencies are greater than the value of alpha except the competency maintaining kitchen premises which has a p value of 0.029. Most of the competencies are not significant, therefore accept the null hypothesis except for the competency “clean and maintain kitchen premises.

The finding of this study is somewhat similar to the findings of Villanueva (2018) in her study “Competencies of Technical-Vocational Teachers of the College of Education: Bases for Comprehensive Training Program.” Result indicated that majority of the

technical- vocational teachers were moderately competent in the various competencies identified by TESDA. For bread and pastry production in particular, faculty are moderately competent and significant to the following competencies: the practice safe and hygienic handling; storage and disposal of food; beverage and materials; and producing accurate and complete data according to the requirements.

Table 7. Comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competency of the pre-service students as perceived by restaurant owners when grouped according to length of operation

Competency	F-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Interpretation
Clean and maintain kitchen premises	0.064	0.801	0.801 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare stocks, sauces and soups	0.398	0.531	0.531 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare appetizers	1.280	0.264	0.264 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare salads and dressings	3.343	0.074	0.074 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare sandwiches	1.888	0.176	0.176 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare meat dishes	0.398	0.531	0.531 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare vegetables dishes	0.906	0.346	0.346 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare egg dishes	0.636	0.429	0.429 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare starch dishes	0.754	0.390	0.390 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare poultry and game dishes	0.873	0.355	0.355 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare seafood dishes	0.082	0.776	0.776 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Prepare desserts	0.002	0.966	0.966 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant
Package prepared food	2.534	0.118	0.118 > 0.05	Accept Ho	Not significant

Table 7 presents the comparison in the level of importance of the pre-service competencies of the on-the-job training students as perceived by restaurant owners when grouped according to length of operation.

Based on the data, no significant difference was found in the level of pre-service student's competency grouped by length of operation since all the p values were greater than the value of alpha which signifies to accept the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. This denotes that the level of importance of the learning outcomes in the pre- service competency of the on-the-job trainees has no significant in the length of operating the business as perceived by restaurant owners.

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine the competency requirements of industry for pre-service students of technical vocational schools based on TESDA training regulations during the school year 2019-2020.

To achieve this purpose, a quantitative-descriptive and qualitative-interview method of research was employed. The respondents of this study were the owners of the 100 industry partners of the technical and vocational schools in the school's division offices of Ilagan City and Isabela. Fifty (50) of these industries are engaged in bread and pastry production and fifty (50) are under cookery industries.

Based on the data gathered, the following were noted:

Most of the bread and pastry business-owners were classified and engaged in a micro type of business while majority of the cookery business-owners were classified and engaged in macro type of business. As to length of operating the industry-partners, most of the bread and pastry businesses are under operation within two years and cookery businesses are under operation for more than two years.

Preparing and producing variant types of products from bread and pastry industries are in their utmost level of importance. Bread and pastry owners therefore highly required the on-the-job trainees in preparing and producing bakery and pastry products where they are highly expected to prepare, decorate and present, and store bakery and pastry products while they are in their on-the-job training. Also, preparing and presenting gateaux, tortes and cakes, preparing and displaying petits fours, and presenting desserts are required by the cake and pastry owners.

Restaurant owners were most concerned with the competency on cleanliness and its maintenances in the various premises of the restaurants where workers prepare variant types of dishes, appetizers and many more. Restaurant owners also perceived the higher importance of preparing sides dishes than preparing the main dishes in the restaurants. The competencies cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises; preparing stocks, sauces and soups; preparing meat dishes; preparing desserts; preparing appetizers; preparing salads and dressings; preparing sandwiches; and preparing vegetable dishes are highly required by the restaurant owners to on-the-job trainees while the following competencies are required: preparing egg dishes; preparing poultry and game dishes; preparing seafood dishes; and preparing starch dishes.

There was no significant difference in the level of importance of the pre-service competencies from the learning outcomes of the on-the-job training students as perceived by bread and pastry owners when grouped according to type of business since the p values of all the competencies are greater than the alpha and are all interpreted not significant.

The significance of p values of all the competencies was greater than the values of alpha except for the competency in maintaining kitchen premises which has a p value of 0.029 which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. The level of importance of the pre-service competencies of the on-the-job training students as perceived by restaurant owners particularly on cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises has a significance in the type of business as perceived by the restaurant owners.

The level of importance of the pre-service competencies from the learning outcomes of the on-the-job training students has no significant in the length of operating the business as perceived by restaurant owners since the p values of the competencies are greater than the value of alpha which signifies to accept the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, this study concludes that the bread and pastry business-owners are categorized as small businessmen who have been operating for less than two years while those engaged in cookery are considered big businessmen who have been into business for two years or more. For bread and pastry owners, knowing how to prepare and produce various types of products from bread and pastry products are considered of utmost importance or highly competency that pre-service students must possess. Meanwhile, restaurant owners put premium on cleanliness and its maintenance as well as the preparation of various types of dishes being the most highly required competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were formulated.

1. Industry partners should extend help to pre-service students/on-the-job trainees to further improve their performance during the duration of their training. Likewise, industry partners should observe and coach the trainees to maximize the competencies they have learned for them to contribute success in the industry.
2. Pre-service students/on-the-job trainees should perform better and execute all the required competencies well in the realization of a successful training that may be applied in the actual and real world of employment.
3. Curriculum planners in the Department of Education and the Technical Education Skills and Development Authority should work hand-in-hand to harmonize the competencies being implemented and see to it that these competencies really match the competencies needed in the industry.

4. School administrators should continue sending competent on-the-job trainees to their respective industry partners, so they can accommodate what the industry really needs and maintain the linkage they have established.
 5. Technical Vocational teachers should focus more on the competencies perceived “highly required” by industry partners.
 6. Technical Vocational teachers should regularly monitor on the-job trainees if competencies are strictly performed and executed. Also, teachers should review the performance rating of the trainees for the purpose of improving the performances of the future student-trainees who will undergo the same training.
 7. Replication study may be undertaken in other business or industry partners to monitor if the required competencies designed by the department of education are executed or performed well.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This original research was carried out to provide a basis for recommending an appropriate and effective mode of delivery. All authors of books, journals, publications, and websites used as references in this study have been properly acknowledged and cited. Consent from the Schools Division Superintendent, School Heads, and Teachers was obtained prior to conducting the study. Additionally, the confidentiality of data and documents generated from respondents' performance is strictly maintained. The data collected will be used exclusively for the purposes of this study.

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REFERENCES

- Abas, M. C., Imam, O. A. (2016). Graduates' Competence on Employability Skills and Job Performance. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, v5 n2 p119-125
- Acob, J. R. (2011). Industry Exposure and Job Readiness of Graduating Students: A Review. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(2), 102-110.
- Bodo, D.D. (2018). Status of the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Technology Program of Eastern Visayas State University: Basis for an Intervention Scheme. Eastern Visayas State University. Tacloban City, Leyte, Philippines
- Cristobal (2008), Mamadra (2005), Mendoza (2008), Mueller (2006), <https://www.slideshare.net/.../factors-that-affect-the-on-the-job-training-of-6528978>
- Demetillo, T. (2016) Technology and Livelihood Education Implementation in K to 12 Curriculum: Basis for Program Enhancement
- Langga, G. (2015). Acquired Competency of Food Service Management Students an Industry Immersion: Basis for Program Intervention. Zamboanga City State Polytechnic College. Zamboanga City.
- Orbeta, A. C., Lagarto, M. B., Ortiz, M.K., Danica, A., Potestad, M. V. (2018) Senior High School and the Labor Market: Perspectives of Grade 12 Students and Human Resource Officers
- Qiuchen Wu, Bin Bai and Xiaolin Zhu (2019). Technical and Vocational Education and Training in the Philippines: Development and Status Quo. Beijing Normal University. Available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332405242>
- Villanueva, J. E. (2018). Competencies of Technical-Vocational Teachers of the College of Education: Bases for Comprehensive Training Program. *African Educational Research Journal*, 6(3), 203-212.
- Wahha, A. (2016). Competency-Based Assessment in the Workplace: A Practical Guide. *Journal of Occupational Training and Development*, 8(3), 65-78.

